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Towards a practice of composition as traceological process. A comparative analysis to *eua'on* by Julio Estrada and *Mycenae-Alpha* by Iannis Xenakis

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Abstract

This paper will present some elements of the state of advancement of a doctoral research project on the topic of digital traces in musical creation. After an introduction presenting elements of terminology and philosophical concern, we will offer an *état de l'art* on the subject of digital traces and digital traceology, followed by an historical review on the compositional process of *eua'on*, a work by Mexican composer Julio Estrada. We will then propose, from a traceological perspective, a comparative analysis of two excerpts of the graphic scores of *eua'on* and *Mycenae-Alpha*, a work by Iannis Xenakis. Such an analysis will reveal some qualities and characteristics of the activity that took place in the *interactive situations* corresponding to the composition of each one of these pieces. We will then give account for a protocol for experimentation and artistic research that attempts to establish the conditions of possibility for a practice of composition as traceology. Conformed by the conjunction capturing-tracking-transferring, such a protocol emerges from our insight into Estrada's work.

From digital trace to digital traceology

Coming from archeology, the concept of traceology is to be understood as a “[...] functional analysis [...] that aims to determine the function of tools by studying the traces produced during their use.”¹ In this research project, digital traceology should be understood as the study of digital traces generated in interactive digital systems. That is to say, the study of energetic-informational *captures* from any kind of human activity,² happening in the context of interactive situations, giving rise to *inscriptions* in memory in digital machines.

In the past recent years, the notion of digital trace, as related to human activity, has become an important topic within a theoretical core in a field of interdisciplinary research that embraces

¹ <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tracéologie>. (last viewed on : 09//19/2019). Translated from french by the author of this paper.

² Although, we would like to embrace in the context of our doctoral research, any kind of activity, be it human, animal, cellular, cosmological, machinical...

various disciplines like anthropology, sociology, cognitive science and computer science.³ Such an interdisciplinary research field deals with issues such as economy of attention, artificial intelligence, cognitive algorithms⁴ and Big Data analysis.

From a philosophical point of view, the problem of the digital trace would be that of its *dissociation* from the context in which it was captured and inscribed. According to François-David Sebbah,⁵ the danger of the digital trace would be:

[...] that the digital trace leads to the point of disjoining the two constituent elements in [productive] tension of the trace [itself] [presence and absence; singularity and repeatability], leaving them falling apart from each other [...]. The risk with digital technology is that it has "too much (intensity of) trace" (too much immediacy because of too much repeatability) and therefore no more trace [...]⁶

In response to this kind of ‘end-of-the-world’⁷ speeches about the digital trace, Cléo Collomb⁸ proposes:

[...] a technological approach to digital traces capable of taking accountability of computational machines [...] a technological concept — that is, a non-anthropocentric concept — of the digital trace. It should be reminded that computing requires from objects and actions that they pass

³ On the subject of digital traces, from a philosophical perspective, see : Cléo Collomb, *Un concept technologique de trace numérique*, doctoral thesis, Université Technologique de Compiègne, (2016) ; the article by François-David Sebbah, « Traces numériques : plus ou moins de fantôme(s) ? » (2015) ; the writings by Louise Merzeau, « Les paradoxes de la mémoire numérique. » (2013) ; « L’intelligence des traces. » (2013) ; « *Embedded memories: patrimonialisation des traces numériques.* » (2011) <http://merzeau.net> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

⁴ Cognitive algorithms and its applications in music is a very recent research topic. A doctoral research project on the subject has just been inaugurated in a collaboration between the IReMUS and the LaBRI, in France.

⁵ François-David Sebbah is a professor of philosophy at Université Paris-Nanterre (source : <https://dep-philo.parisnanterre.fr/navigation/les-enseignants/sebbah-francois-david-548260.kjsp>) (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

⁶ François-David Sebbah, « Traces numériques : plus ou moins de fantôme(s) ? », in *Le sujet digital*, Larsonneur, Claire, Regnaud, Arnaud, Cassou-Noguès, Pierre, Touiza, Sara, (ed.), Paris, Les presses du réel, 2015, p. 124 - 125. The citation is translated from french by the author of this paper.

⁷ Internet music dealers such as Google, Spotify, Facebook and You Tube make use of digital tracing (tracking). The statistical methods they use to process the information (*i.e.* digital traces) coming from the users of these platforms only takes into account temporal markers. Such an approach ignores the dynamics of musical listening. The effect of this kind of method is to induce even more normativity — a formatted, standardised, way of listening to music — to enclose listening into a matrix of social and cultural control dominated by the laws of the market.

⁸ Cléo Collomb holds a PhD in Philosophy from the Compiègne University of Technology and the Université Libre de Bruxelles. She defended a dissertation on digital traceability and ways of living with computational machines. She is currently research engineer on ANR ENEID project (source : <https://ucompiègne.academia.edu/Cl%C3%A9oCollomb>) (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

through digital inscription to exist, computational machines are involved in the process of production of digital traces, that a ‘technological semiotics’ would allow to describe.⁹

How such a process of production of digital traces could inform us about the process that leads to the emergence of musicality? In view of what is established by the precedent elements of reflection presented in this introduction, and from the perspective of a composer engaged in musicological research, one of the emergent questions from our analysis is that of the role of *corporeality* in the poetics of composers. If by using computational methods, it could be possible to give account for the relationship between the body, imaginary and musicality, what can digital traces — understood as transferred corporeal dynamism — teach us about what takes place in the realm of interactive situations with sound?

Digital traces involve body dynamics taking place in a particular context of interactivity, such as that of improvisation with computers. Although, compositional processes mediated by computers involve at least some level of interactivity, yet not always demanding a corporeal engagement from the composer. Our aim is to study those cases where there is a composer’s strong corporeal dynamic engagement, which is then captured and inscribed in artificial memory, in particular those cases where this data is turned into material for compositional activity.

Digital traces in musicological research

In the field of musicological research, a methodology based on the use of digital traces for the analysis of electroacoustic music interpretation is currently being developed¹⁰ in a project led by Pierre Couprie¹¹ at IReMUS,¹² where Couprie has created *motuslabtool*,¹³ a software allowing for recording and analysing the gestures of performers as they interpret electroacoustic works.

⁹ Cléo Collomb, *Un concept technologique de trace numérique*, doctoral thesis under the direction of François-David SEBBAH and Thomas BERNIS, Compiègne University of Technology and Université Libre de Bruxelles, 2016, p.5.

¹⁰ <http://www.iremusc.cnrs.fr/fr/programme-de-recherche/analyse-de-linterpretation-acousmatique> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

¹¹ Pierre Couprie is lecturer at Sorbonne Université, Institut de Recherche en Musicologie (IReMUS) http://www.pierrecooprie.fr/?page_id=173 (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

¹² IReMUS, Institut de Recherche en Musicologie (Institut of Research in Musicology at Sorbonne Université)

¹³ *motuslabtool*, is downloadable at http://logiciels.pierrecooprie.fr/?page_id=1695 (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

Furthermore, the use of digital traces may as well be related to a particular domain of research dealing with the statistical analysis of data collections, Music Information Retrieval (MIR),¹⁴ a research domain that has produced an important body of documentary sources and technical developments, and which aims at the implementation of methods for computational analysis of digital musical streams. The automated organisation of musical play-lists by means of semantic databases, in the domain of commercial distribution of music in the Internet, is one example of the application of knowledge generated by the type of research such as MIR.¹⁵

Closer to our enquiry interests, the interdisciplinary research work on Roger Reynolds's¹⁶ *The Angel of Death*,¹⁷ a one of a kind investigation initiative,¹⁸ on which it was made usage of a database created from what the audience expressed while listening to Reynolds's piece in concert. The database was built through a real-time sensor interface,¹⁹ crafted by an IRCAM²⁰ team.²¹ The function of such a device was to provide the means for a dynamic capture of the gestures of the audience, turning them into information for statistical analysis. The analysis of the data collected during the concert had to provide information about the perception of

¹⁴ Music Information Retrieval (MIR). « Music information retrieval (MIR) is the interdisciplinary science of retrieving information from music. MIR is a small but growing field of research with many real-world applications. Those involved in MIR may have a background in musicology, psychoacoustics, psychology, academic music study, signal processing, informatics, machine learning, optical music recognition, computational intelligence or some combination of these. » Source : https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Music_information_retrieval See also the web page of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR) : <https://www.ismir.net/> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

¹⁵ On that matter, see for example the WASABI project : « [...] the WASABI project, started in 2017, which aims at (1) the construction of a 2 million song knowledge base that combines metadata collected from music databases on the Web, metadata resulting from the analysis of song lyrics, and metadata resulting from the audio analysis, and (2) the development of semantic applications with high added value to exploit this semantic database. » in Gabriel Meseguer-Brocal, Geoffroy Peeters, Guillaume Pellerin, Michel Buffa, Elena Cabrio, Catherine Faron Zucker, Alain Giboin, Isabelle Mirbel, Romain Hennequin, Manuel Moussallam, et al., « WASABI: a Two Million Song Database Project with Audio and Cultural Metadata plus WebAudio enhanced Client Application » <https://hal.univ-cotedazur.fr/hal-01589250/document> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

¹⁶ Roger Reynolds, born in 1934 in Detroit in the state of Michigan USA. Studies composition with Roberto Gherard. Pulitzer Prize 1989 *Whispers out of time*, for string orchestra, (1988).

¹⁷ *The Angel of Death*, for solo piano, chamber orchestra and computer-processed sounds on a 6-channel system. Commissioned by IRCAM, world premiere in Paris in 2001, Festival Agora.

¹⁸ Project hosted at Ircam and led by Stephen McAdams, with whom Roger Reynolds had already collaborated in 1983 as part of the project *Archipelago*, for orchestra and tape (1983).

¹⁹ Technical information related to the system developed by Bennett Smith for *The Angel of Death* project can be reached at : <http://recherche.ircam.fr/pcm/bks/death/frames.html> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁰ IRCAM, Institut de Recherche et Coordination Acoustique Musique (Institute for Research and Coordination in Acoustics/Music)

²¹ The research team Perception et Cognition Musicales (PCM) archives can be reached at : <http://recherche.ircam.fr/> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

formal elements of the piece during its execution. According to Stephen McAdams,²² the goal of this project was:

[...] to bring objective elements of reflection to questions raised within a research approach that marries the methods and frameworks of the cognitive sciences with the human sciences in the domain of music.²³

Here, the idea of asking the public about their perception of a musical flow being unveiled in concert, and to capture this information through a digital sensor device — leading to a set of digital traces — remains to our knowledge a *première*.

Digital traces in musical creation

Concerning musical creation, practices and approaches using either traces, imprints, tracks or even borrowed materials, could be examples of creative behaviour linked to the problematic we are trying to build from the perspective of the digital trace phenomenon. Christian Marclay²⁴ and his collages composed by mixing vinyl records can be mentioned on the use of borrowed materials.²⁵ For Nicolas Donin,²⁶ an important precedent of what he calls, an aesthetics of the imprint,²⁷ is Gérard Grisey's²⁸ proposal for an “instrumental synthesis”, which can be heard at the end of his work *Périodes*,²⁹ and which was composed *from the image* of a sonogram analysis of a sound spectrum. This is an historical example of the use of a visual representation of the analysis of natural phenomena for the means of composition and orchestration.

²² Stephen McAdams was a researcher at IRCAM (in 1986). He is currently professor at McGill University and Canada Research Chair in Musical Perception and Cognition (in 2015). Source : https://data.bnf.fr/fr/12167786/stephen_mcadams/ (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²³ Stephen McAdams, Translated from Stephen McAdams, *Perception et cognition de la musique*, Editions J. Vrin, Paris, 2015. (Chapter 4, The temporality of music listening, p.4). Source : http://www.music.mcgill.ca/~smc/McAdams_2015_PCM_Chap4b.pdf (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁴ Christian Marclay, (1955) is a musician, composer and artist. His interdisciplinary work explores the relationship between photography, video, film and sound. Source : https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christian_Marclay (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁵ Source : https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christian_Marclay (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁶ Nicolas Donin, musicologist at IRCAM, founder and leader of the research team Analyse des Pratiques Musicales (Analysis of musical practices). Source : <https://symetrie.com/fr/auteurs/nicolas.donin> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁷ <https://www.college-de-france.fr/site/philippe-manoury/symposium-2017-06-06-12h00.htm> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁸ Gérard Grisey, French composer, born in 1946 and died in 1998. His work is associated with the "spectral movement". https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/G%C3%A9rard_Grisey (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

²⁹ *Périodes* (1974), for flute, trombone, violin, viola, cello and double-bass.

On the other way around, Philippe Leroux³⁰ has made usage of gestural imprints, yet capturing them into digital devices. In his work *VOI(REX)*,³¹ the spatialisation is controlled by gesture information captured off-line. By means of a digital interface such as a mouse, Leroux ‘hand-wrote’ somme words coming from the same text chosen by the composer for the work.³² Once captured in the digital realm and transferred to a C.A.C³³ environment, the data issued from the *dynamics* and the *forms* of Leroux handwriting was given different functions like programming the parameters for the spatialisation of the electronic part of the fifth movement of the piece.³⁴ This technique was also employed by the composer in *Extended Apocalypse*.³⁵ Furthermore, in *Quid sit Musicus*,³⁶ Leroux enlarged this practice by taking as a calligraphic referent the manuscript of *Ma fin est mon commencement*, by Guillaume de Machaut. Leroux proceeds by over-writing the pneumatic notations found on a copy of Machaut’s manuscript while at the same time, capturing the dynamism of his hand movements by means of an interactive paper interface,³⁷ then turning the dynamic forms coming from his hand strokes into materials for the composition of the rhythmic, harmonic and melodic elements of the work.

³⁰ Philippe Leroux, born in 1959 in Boulogne sur Seine (France). Since September 2011 he has been Associate Professor of Composition at the Schulich School of Music at McGill University, where he also directs the Digital Composition Studio. He is currently in residence at the MEITAR ensemble in Tel Aviv. Source : <http://www.lerouxcomposition.com/fr/pages/bio.html> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

³¹ *VOI(REX)*, (2002), for unspecified solo voice, flute, clarinet, violin, cello, piano, percussionist and live electronics, 23’. Source: <http://brahms.ircam.fr/works/work/14267/> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

³² A text written by Lin Delpierre, photographer and writer born in 1962 in Bayonne. Source : <http://www.lindelpierre.net/html/biographie.html> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

³³ Computer Assisted Composition. As a long time partner at the IRCAM, Leroux has contributed to the development of the *Open Music* platform.

³⁴ See the article by Philippe Leroux, « The Model of the Model in *VOI(REX)* », in BRESSON, Jean, AGON, Carlos, ASSAYAG, Gérard, (ed.), *The OM Composer’s Book .2*, Paris, Delatour, 2006.

³⁵ *Extended Apocalypse*, (2011), for 2 solo soprano, mezzo-soprano solo, baritone solo, flute, oboe, clarinet, bassoon, horn, trumpet, trombone, 2 percussionist, harp, piano, violin, viola, cello, double bass and live electronics, 20’. Source : <http://brahms.ircam.fr/works/work/31052/> (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

³⁶ *Quid sit Musicus*, (2014), for lute (also guitar), fiddle (also cello), unspecified choir and live electronics, 18’. Source: <http://brahms.ircam.fr/works/work/34947/>. (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

³⁷ On the development of this kind of interface see the doctoral thesis by Jérémie Garcia, *Supporting music composition with interactive paper*, Université Paris Sud - Paris XI, 2014.

From *eua'on* to *eua'on'ome*

In 1980, Mexican composer Julio Estrada³⁸ composed *eua'on*,³⁹ for UPIC,⁴⁰ a piece entirely composed of synthesised sounds. Characterised by its violently sounding continuity, the compositional experience involved in the creation of this work will lead the composer's process from a conception of sound — the continuous macro-timbre ; to the creation of a composition method — the chrono-acoustic transcription method ; to an aesthetic project : the *continuum*.⁴¹ After having already consolidated the main lines of his work with the *continuum*⁴² Estrada will compose, between 1994 and 1995, *eua'on'ome*,⁴³ for orchestra, a transferential sequel of *eua'on*. This case is of particular concern in the sense that Estrada leads his creative process from the composition of an electronic music work, to the composition of a piece for large orchestra, maintaining a *genetic link* between both pieces. A very important aspect of the creative process engaged in the composition of this two works is that it encompasses the use of technology both as a memorial device and as a mediation one, within an interactive approach to composition. Moreover, the UPIC allowed the composition of synthetic sounds by drawing, giving place to a 'graphic score'. The analogical correspondence between these graphics and the sound results as well as the interactive context of their production and the transfer of the information captured during the *interactive experience* to the instrumental domain signify, in the framework of this research project, a

³⁸ Estrada was born in Mexico City in 1943. After studying with Julian Orbon, Jean Etienne Marie, Karlheinz Stockhausen, György Ligeti and Olivier Messiaen he becomes near to Iannis Xenakis with whom he maintained a close relationship. In 1994, he defended his doctoral thesis in musicology, *Théorie de la composition: discontinuum - continuum* (Theory of composition: *discontinuum - continuum*), at the University of Strasbourg, under the direction of François Bernard-Mâche. Appointed Knight of the Order of Arts in 1981 and 1986. Currently he is a member of the National Institute of Aesthetic Research of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) and professor of composition at the Faculty of Music (UNAM).

³⁹ *eua'on*, was composed for the UPIC in 1980, as part of a time of residency at the CEMAMu. This is the only electronic work that figures in the catalogue of Estrada. It has a duration of 7'44. It was published in the double CD compilation *Xenakis, UPIC, Continuum Electroacoustic & Instrumental works from CCMIX Paris*, on Mode Records (mode 98/99), in 2001.

⁴⁰ *Unité Polyagogique du CEMAMu* (Polyagogic Unit of CEMAMu) (UPIC) was developed by Iannis Xenakis at the Center for Mathematical and Automatic Musical Studies (CEMAMu) in Paris in 1977. Xenakis used it for *Mycenae-Alpha* (1978). The UPIC is a graphic tablet, connected to a computer, with a vector display. The user draws waveforms and envelopes, which are then processed by the computer. The x-axis represents the time and the y-axis the frequencies. They can also be transposed, flipped, inverted and subject to several transformation algorithms. The system allows real-time performance by moving the stylus on the tablet. Source: <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/UPIC> (Last viewed on : 09/19/2019).

⁴¹ See : Julio Estrada, « Le continuum en musique : structure et ouvertures en composition, ses dérivations esthétiques », in *Ästhetik und Komposition. Zur Aktualität der Darmstädter Ferienkursearbeit*, edited by Gianmario Borio and Ulrich Mosch, Mainz, Schott, 1994, p. 50–65.

⁴² *yuunohui'yei* (1983) for cello, *ishini'ioni* (1984-1990) for string quartet, *yuunohui'nahui* (1985) for double-bass, *yuunohui'se* (1990) for violin, *yuunohui'ome* (1990) for viola.

⁴³ *eua'on'ome*, for large orchestra (1994-95), ca. 11', also published on the same 2001 compilation on Mode Records. Recorded by the SWF Orchestra of Baden-Baden, Olaf Henzold, conductor.

very important precedent of what could be a practice of *composition as a traceological process*.

A traceological comparative analysis to *eua'on* by Julio Estrada and *Mycenae-Alpha* by Iannis Xenakis

Let us take the opportunity of a comparative analysis, from a traceological point of view, of two excerpts of 'graphic scores' drawn with the UPIC. Figure 1 displays, on the left-hand, an excerpt taken from *eua'on* by Estrada ; on the other hand, an excerpt from *Mycenae-Alpha*⁴⁴ by Iannis Xenakis.⁴⁵

Fig. 1. Side by side, an excerpt of *eua'on*, by Julio Estrada, an excerpt of *Mycenae-Alpha*, by Iannis Xenakis.

What we observe in the case of Estrada is first of all, a fairly intense *gestural activity* giving rise to a very dense graphic and aural texture. It looks like an approach that proceeds by the accumulation of the same type of gesture. Meanwhile, on the side of the *Mycenae-Alpha* excerpt, we observe a gestural activity that could in turn be associated to a more reflexive attitude in regards to what should come to be a sound texture obtained by means of drawing. This is an approach that seems to proceed by composing the sound from an idea — a mental image — of a drawing. Whilst in the case of *eua'on*, the analogy ratio between gesture, graphic and sound seems to be narrower.

Moreover, a dramatic component can be stated as we observe the graphic traces of what was the experience of creation of *eua'on*. Indeed, the blackened accumulation of lines that crosses

⁴⁴ *Mycenae-Alpha* (1978), for UPIC, 10'. Published on *Xenakis, UPIC, Continuum Electroacoustic & Instrumental works from CCMIX Paris*, on Mode Records (mode 98/99), in 2001.

⁴⁵ Iannis Xenakis was born on May 29, 1922 in Brăila, Romania and died on February 4, 2001 in Paris. Of greek origin, architect and engineer, and one of the most innovative composers of the 20th century. Source : https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Iannis_Xenakis (Last viewed on : 09//19/2019).

the space of the abscissae and ordinate at a seemingly tight speed regime, in the middle of the excerpt, violently splits the score, yet without inducing a breaking-off in the flow of sound energy. This rises the idea of a rather ‘obsessive-compulsive-being in trance’ mind and emotional state, taking over at this particular point of what was the experience of composition of Estrada’s piece.⁴⁶ At this point, it may be allowed to say that we are here in presence of a process in which, situated in a *dialogical relationship with sound*, the structural coupling of listening (*i.e* inner-listening) with the dynamism of the body informs the construction of a dramaturgy which would be that of a listening-in-emergence⁴⁷ (*i.e* the birth of listening or the deconstruction and re-construction of listening). We conclude that, in the case of *eua'on* it is rather a *performative listening* — *i.e* listening-in-the-making — that outweighs the graphic dimension of the experience.

At this point, it becomes necessary to underline, at the conclusion of this brief analytical passage, two very important aspects. First, as to the nature of the analysed objects, it must be pointed out that this are not more graphic representations of sound, than *graphic traces of what was a sensorial and interactive experience of sound*. By making it possible to compose the sound by drawing, the UPIC generates at the same time *the traces of its use*. Indeed, these drawings are much more the graphic traces of the utilisation of the UPIC than graphic musical scores. Secondly, these traces tell us about the relationship between two domains of reality coexisting in the interactive experience with sound and musical environments such as the UPIC : what we observe is the *traces of a dynamism of the body* involved in the composition of a dynamism of sound.

In-forming listening by capturing, *trace*-ing and transferring data from interactive situations

From both the historical and analytical elements of our exposé, it is possible to deduce a synthesised conceptual structure of the creative process involving analogue and digital traces. Such a structure can be turned into a protocol for the means of research and creative experimentation, and it can be established in a preliminary way by an operative conjunction in three terms : *capture-trace-transfer*. In this triple-sided set which constitutes, from our point of view, the stages of the traceological creative process :

⁴⁶ In the booklet the CD compilation *Xenakis, UPIC, Continuum Electroacoustic & Instrumental works from CCMIX Paris*, Estrada states about the process of composition of *eua'on* : « I refused to symbolise musically the loss of my father by a long silence of several months. Then I was able to access the creation of a music certainly brutal but perfectly analogous to the rage of my pain. » *eua'on* means ‘to fly’ or ‘to fly again’, according to what the composer stated in his key note given at the Electroacoustic Music Studies Network Conference, on June 2019, at La Casa del Lago in Mexico City.

⁴⁷ We make use of the term ‘emergence’ in the sense of Varela and Maturana’s theory of cognition. Musicality as musical listening could be understood as an emergent quality (knowledge) that emerges from the interaction between autonomous entities. On the subject of embodied cognition and inactive theory, see : Varela, Francisco J.; Thompson, Evan; Rosch, Eleanor, *The embodied mind: Cognitive science and human experience*, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, USA. 1991. See also: Humberto R. Maturana; Francisco J. Varela; *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living*, Springer, 1991.

- *Capturing* should be understood as the operation of exchanging information between the interactive sound stream and the dynamically engaged body. It deals with the data entry and data collecting operation in the context of dialogical situations taking place in interactive sound environments.

- *Tracing* involves interrogating the data collected during the capture processes in order to determine what might function as *material* for compositional purposes. Here the composer, in the manner of an archaeologist or archivist, studies the data structures generated in the environment, and thus determines about their relevance for a composition project to be realised.

- *Transferring* the structures retained from the data captured in the field of interactivity to that of musical interpretation. It is the operation that leads to the enactment of what has been given during the previous stages and thus to establish, ideally, the conditions so that the interactive-dialogical situation can be formally re-actualised.

Conclusion

We presented an *état de l'art* about digital traces that gave account of historical elements in musicological research and in musical creation. We then offered, from a traceological perspective, a comparative analysis of works by Julio Estrada and Iannis Xenakis. At this point, it should be underlined that what came to inform our descriptions of these experiences of creation is a set of drawings (*tracées*), withholding a particular status not only for the purposes of this particular traceological analysis, but perhaps also for what could be a more accurate description of a compositional environment such as that proposed by Xenakis. From the observation of the traces left by these creative experiences, the purpose of our analysis was to find elements that can inform us as to the qualities of what it was the experience of listening in the context of an interactive situation involving sound. The graphical traces that we compared in this paper are obviously analogical however, a digital computer was at the core of the device having captured and collected these traces. This means that these graphic traces may have had at some point a *digital correlate*. In the singular case of the UPIC environment, this digital correlativity has a particular function, that of the mediation between graphic and sound textures, and thus serves to establish a structural coupling between gesture and listening, similar to that taking place during the playing of a musical instrument. This digital correlate is the digital complementary part of the analog graphic trace. An analysis of this digital component could inform us in quantitative terms about the compositional experience of both *eua'on* and *Mycenae-Alpha*. Beyond enriching our description criteria concerning this type of sensorial and creative experience, what would be the compositional purpose of an analysis of such *dynamic digital traces* resulting from this kind of interactive situations involving sound ?

Concerning the relationship between the electronic work, *eua'on*, and the orchestral one, *eua'on'ome*, by Estrada, while giving rise to a new way of approaching instrumental composition by means of exploring the orchestral potentials of what we consider as a set of inscriptions — a set of traces — within the very own creative and historical process of the composer himself, Estrada amplified at the same time his own poetic environment. In fact,

the relationship between *eua'on* and *eua'on'ome* withholds, in the system that thus it constitutes, a set of characteristics that place this couple of pieces in a particular terrain of compositional activity. Such an approach to composition stands near to what we conceive as *composition as a traceological process*. In the forthcoming outputs of our investigations, these two music works will be of a very particular interest. Indeed, we still have to determine to what extent analogical and digital traces played an important part in the genetic link between both pieces, and thus in the composition of *eua'on'ome*.

Furthermore, capturing, tracing and transferring, in the context of a formalised digital convergence suggest an approach to musical creation involving a convertibility between structures and operations. In this sense, we believe that a set of propositions based on this methodology will allow us to test, for compositional intentions, different kinds of digital traces in their potentials, both operative and structuring.

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